

Efficient water splitting via a flexible solar-powered Hybrid thermochemical-Sulphur dioxide depolarized Electrolysis Cycle

Energy demand analysis of a practical solar hybrid sulfur cycle: the HySelect project

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Background

Image source: [Clifford \(2017\)](#)

Background

*Thermochemical process efficiency is based on the hydrogen lower heating value (LHV)

(1) Gorensek et al. [1]: Thermochemical process efficiency of 35%

(2) Niehoff et al. [2]: Thermochemical process efficiency of 35%

(3) Gorensek et al. [3]: Thermochemical process efficiency of 35%

No pilot and demonstration plant yet!!

Objective

- Energy demand analysis of a Solar Hybrid Sulfur Cycle from **practical point of view for the implementation of a demonstration plant.**
- Example of the practical point: Operating pressure of sulfuric acid decomposition section and SO₂-depolarized electrolyzer section is slightly under ambient pressure.

Centrifugal particle receiver

Image source: [Ebert et al. \(2019\)](#)

Concept of the demonstration plant

Method

HyS: Hybrid Sulfur Cycle
SDE: SO₂-Depolarized Electrolyzer

HyS solar thermal - thermochemical plant

HyS chemical - electrochemical plant

Concept of the demonstration plant

Method

HyS: Hybrid Sulfur Cycle
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HyS solar thermal - thermochemical plant

HyS chemical - electrochemical plant

Method

- Molar flow rate of SO₂ after the SO₃ decomposer is fixed to 0.12 mol/s
- Conversion rate of the SO₃ decomposer is set to 63% (consider catalytic degradation)

Concept of the demonstration plant

Method

HyS: Hybrid Sulfur Cycle
SDE: SO₂-Depolarized Electrolyzer

HyS solar thermal - thermochemical plant

HyS chemical - electrochemical plant

Method

Image source: GRILLO-Werke AG

Concept of the demonstration plant

Method

HyS: Hybrid Sulfur Cycle
SDE: SO₂-Depolarized Electrolyzer

HyS solar thermal - thermochemical plant

HyS chemical - electrochemical plant

Results and discussions

* SO₂ conversion rate in SDE is fixed at 50%

Parameter	Our study	Niehoff et al. [2]	Gorensek et al. [3]
Target H ₂ production rate	0.06 mol/s	0.13 kmol/s	1 kmol/s
Applied thermal energy to H ₂ SO ₄ decomposition process	43 kW _{th}	86 MW _{th}	353 MW _{th}
Operating pressure in H ₂ SO ₄ decomposition process	1 bar(a)	1 bar(a)	14.1 bar(a)
Maximum temperature in H ₂ SO ₄ decomposition process	850 °C	1300 °C	850 °C
Consumed electric power in SDE	8 kW _{el}	15 MW _{el}	116 MW _{el}
Operating pressure in SDE	1 bar(a)	12 bar(a)	22.7 bar(a)
Operating temperature in SDE	70 °C	74 °C	123 °C
Energy efficiency for hydrogen production	25%	33%	41%

- Energy efficiency calculation

$$\eta_{en} = \frac{\dot{m}_{H_2,out} \cdot LHV_{H_2}}{\dot{W}_{elec} + \dot{Q}_{heat}}$$

$\dot{m}_{H_2,out}$: Outlet mass flow rate of hydrogen [kg/s]

LHV_{H_2} : Hydrogen lower heating value [J/kg]

\dot{W}_{elec} : Total electrical energy input [W_{el}]

\dot{Q}_{heat} : Total thermal energy input [W_{th}]

Summary

25% of energy efficiency (provisional results)

Aspen plus model

Future study

- Complete the investigation of chemical – electrochemical plant (Block (4), (5), and (6)).
- Complete the energy demand analysis with the final plant concept.
- Integrate the solar particle receiver concept into the Aspen model.
- Complete the techno-economic study of the concept.

References

- [1] Gorenssek MB, Summers W (2009) Hybrid sulfur flowsheets using PEM electrolysis and a bayonet decomposition reactor. Int J Hydrogen Energ 34:4097–4114.
- [2] Guerra Niehoff A, Bayer Botero N, Acharya A et al. (2015) Process modelling and heat management of the solar hybrid sulfur cycle. Int J Hydrogen Energ 40:4461–4473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.01.168>
- [3] Gorenssek MB, Corgnale C, Summers WA (2017) Development of the hybrid sulfur cycle for use with concentrated solar heat. I. Conceptual design. Int J Hydrogen Energ 42:20939–20954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.06.241>

HySelect⁺₁₆⁻

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HySelect Jülich

At the HySelect Jülich site, all solar thermal & thermochemical processes are located.

HySelect Duisburg

At the HySelect Duisburg site, all chemical & electrochemical processes are located.

Concept of the demonstration plant

Method

HyS: Hybrid Sulfur Cycle
SDE: SO₂-Depolarized Electrolyzer

HyS solar thermal - thermochemical plant

HyS chemical - electrochemical plant

Method

- Pressurized air (5 bar) is used to drive the compressor and cool the compressed gas

SDE: SO₂-Depolarized Electrolyzer

Method

- 363 g/s
- 68 °C
- 1 bar
- 15 wt% H₂SO₄, 83 wt% H₂O, 2 wt% SO₂

Anode in

Cathode in

- 150 g/s
- 68 °C
- 1 bar
- 15 wt% H₂SO₄, 85 wt% H₂O

200 °C

Dummy steam flow for electricity consumption

SDE User-Defined Block

- Heat generation
- Electricity consumption
- Outlet flow composition
- Water cross-over

Dummy steam flow for heat generation

200 °C

Anode out 1

Cathode out 1

200 °C

Anode out 2

Cathode out 2

- 359 g/s
- 72 °C
- 1 bar
- 17 wt% H₂SO₄, 82 wt% H₂O, 1 wt% SO₂

- 155 g/s
- 72 °C
- 1 bar
- 14.5 wt% H₂SO₄, 85.4 wt% H₂O, 0.1 wt% H₂

200 °C

- Produced hydrogen is compressed and separated.
- Down stream process is still under investigation.

Method

- Liquid-fed catholyte and anolyte compartments are considered.
- 5-15 wt% of H₂SO₄ is considered in anolyte and catholyte to obtain reasonable high reactant solubility.
- Nafion 117 is considered as a SDE's membrane. It was reported to have the least SO₂ transfer capability from anolyte to catholyte.
- Water crossover phenomena are considered in our model. Only the water crossover due to electro-osmotic drag is considered since it has the greatest impact of all other causes.
- SO₂ crossover is not considered in our model so far.
- Current density value of 5000 A/m² is used.
- Total cell potential value of 0.7 V is used in our study.
- SO₂ conversion rate of 20-50% is considered.
- Cell temperature is adjusted between 20-95 °C

Method

- 86 °C hot water (input) carries 40 kW_{th}
- 8 °C chilled water (output) carries 29 kW_{th}

Method

HALDOR TOPSOE

Wet gas Sulfuric Acid (WSA) unit

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Hybrid Sulfur Cycle

Heat

Ni

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(2) Niehoff et al. [2]: Thermochemical process efficiency of 35%

Hybrid Sulfur Cycle

(3) Gorensek et al. [3]: Thermochemical process efficiency of 35%

Hybrid Sulfur Cycle

Heat

Falling particle concentrated solar receiver

Electricity

Bayonet decomposition reactor

Image source: [Gorensek et al. \(2009\)](#)